

WASTE 4think

MOVING TOWARDS LIFE CYCLE THINKING BY INTEGRATING ADVANCED WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

Ecosolution:

**“BIOMASS PRODUCT”
VALORIZATION OF KITCHEN/
FOOD WASTE**

Fermentable Household Waste (FHW) will be separately collected by Municipality of Halandri, in collaboration with NTUA and ENBIO to generate FORBI (a Food Residue Biomass product) through drying and shredding

HALANDRI

WHY?

To evaluate this material as potential feedstock for the production of fuels and high-grade materials

such as...

ELECTRICITY

**BIOGAS
BIOETHANOL**

**ACTIVATED
CARBON**

COMPOST

ANIMAL FEED

PELLETS

**ALTERNATIVE FUEL
FOR THE CEMENT
INDUSTRY**

Ecosolution:

BIOFUELS AND COMPOST PRODUCTION FROM DISPOSABLE NAPPIES

Collection of expired food products (supermarkets) and disposable nappies (nurseries and elderly houses) by Municipality of Halandri in collaboration with Green Technologies Ltd and University of Patras

WHY?

The mixture of hydrogen and methane (hythane) after upgrading will be either injected in the natural gas grid where the selected nursery is connected to or will be fed directly to the nursery's burner to cover partially its thermal needs.

The produced digestate (solid fraction of anaerobic effluent)

COMPOST

The recovered material may be forwarded to plastic and other relevant companies

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